

THE TRANS-EUROPEAN SUTURE ZONE IN ROMANIA

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Introduction

The EUROPROBE project, developed since the early '90 for more than a decade, investigated old geological and geophysical traces of large scale tectonic events from the Atlantic Ocean till the Ural Mts.

One of its most interesting and challenging subproject was Trans-European Suture Zone (TESZ), its main tasks being: a) to investigate and geologically interpret a large area of terranes accretion to ancient European lithosphere and b) to detect the trans-continental tectonic boundary of old European cratons (Baltic and East European), from the North Sea to the Black Sea.

TESZ northern and eastern geotectonic boundaries are rarely outcropping and their deepward development is far from being vertical; many times this tectonic contact is concealed by overlapping geological structures, due to subduction and soft collision processes.

Across Europe from the North Sea till the Carpathian Mts., geological techniques (field mapping, deep boreholes cores sampling and analysing) and relevant geophysical methods (refraction seismics, seismic tomography, magnetotelluric soundings, gravity, magnetics) have been employed to understand the tectonic processes that led to microcontinents amalgamation during geological time and build models for the TESZ areal development and in-depth geometry.

When TESZ eastern boundary, either as TTZ (Tornquist-Teisseyre Zone) or TTL (Tornquist-Teisseyre Line), reached the Carpathians, numerous northern and western geoscientists considered that area as its south-eastern end. A part of eastern geologists advocated the idea that this geotectonic boundary should follow eastward along the southern boundary of the East European Platform, in Romania, Moldavia and Ukraine.

Previous models on TESZ eastern boundary in Romania

Romanian geophysicists considered that TESZ continues southward beneath the East Carpathians overthrust structures, in Ukraine and Romania, towards the Black Sea.

M. Visarion interpreted available regional geophysical (gravity, magnetic /aeromagnetic, electromagnetic) and geological regional data and built a model describing TTZ in Romania. The eastern TTZ boundary follows the Rava Ruska Fault (Ukraine), Siret Fault (Romania) and Vaslui– Cetatea Alba faults (Romania and Ukraine), the latter segment changing the NW-SE trending to W–E. The TTZ western boundary of this model, situated beneath the East Carpathians sedimentary structures is parallel to the eastern one till the East Carpathians Bend Zone, keeping towards the Black Sea the NW-SE trending. Between the Carpathians and the Black Sea this boundary is following the Capidava-Ovidiu Fault.

Stanica et al. (1999) interpreted TESZ boundary on regional transects with magnetotelluric soundings crossing the East Carpathians and their foreland. Significant westward decreases in crustal and lithospheric thickness, at the boundary between the platform (Scythian or East European) and the Transylvanian tectonic block, were considered as main criteria to detect this concealed geotectonic contact. Besides the TESZ location beneath the Carpathians, the southern part of the model uses the Peceneaga-Camena Fault as limit towards the Black Sea.

Besutiu et al. (2004), interpreting regional gravity, magnetic and magnetotelluric soundings data, consider that the TTZ boundary has been shifted westward for hundreds of km from the East Carpathians Bend Zone, along the Trans-Getica Fault, on the Serbian and Bulgarian territories.

A.-I. Pantia (2018), in a M.Sc. Thesis, analysing a large quantity of geological and geophysical data, such as the model of the Miechow Depression southern continuation beneath the Carpathians till the Alexandria Depression (Sandulescu, 1984) and the newest seismic tomography data (van der Meer et al., 2018a), built the TESZ model between the East Carpathians and Danube river by including the Focsani and Alexandria depressions.

The Trans-European Suture Zone in Romania

This study started in late '90, during the involvement of the first author in the Trans-European Suture Zone project, and lasted for 20 years. The collaboration with young geoscientists as co-authors, either for M.Sc. or Ph.D. theses, represented the best reason for completing this research towards concluding results.

At a broad regional scale, the first geodetic-geophysical analysed data are those provided by the 1997 European Gravimetric Geoid. The geoidal anomalies processed during the late '90 have been presented in 2000 at the TESZ Session (European Geophysical Society Conference, Nice,) and recently published by Ioane & Stanciu (2018).

Fig. 1 – A: EGG 97 filtered geoidal anomalies along TESZ;
B: Map showing the variability of geoidal heights with distance
(Ioane & Stanciu, 2018)

The straight NW-SE lineament with rapid variations of the geoid heights, noticed within Poland, Ukraine and Romania, is abruptly shifted in Romania at the East Carpathians Bend Zone. After this NE-SW displacement, the lineament regains its NW-SE trending towards the

Black Sea, in Romania and Bulgaria. The rapid increase in geoidal heights across the lineament is determined by deep density inhomogeneities determined by the western boundary of the East European Platform with the European Palaeozoic Platform, the Panonnian Basin, Tisza-Dacia tectonic block and the Moesian Platform. The thinner crust and lithosphere of the westerly located tectonic blocks, as compared to the East European Platform, determine the sudden increase of the geoidal values over short distances along TESZ, due to an uplifted position of higher density upper mantle rocks (Ioane & Stanciu, 2018).

Fig. 2 – MagSat satellite magnetic anomalies in Central and Eastern Europe (Purucker, 1979). The red-dashed line represents the interpreted Trans European Suture Zone eastern boundary (Ioane & Stanciu, 2015)

At a continental scale, the satellite MagSat geomagnetic field variations (Purucker, 1997), shown in Fig. 2, illustrate a significant westward decrease along the NW-SE trending TESZ boundary in Poland and Ukraine. A weaker magnetic variation may be also observed across Romania and northern Bulgaria, as well as a change in direction (NW-SE to NNW-SSE), the continuation of this regional tectonic lineament being still visible. The fact that the interpreted TESZ lineament crosses southward the Moesian Platform may be explained in two ways: a) the East European Platform (EEP) western boundary is here deeply located, beneath the Moesian Platform; b) the eastern compartment of the Moesian Platform (situated between the Intramoesian Fault and the Black Sea) represents a tectonic block having high similarities with the EEP (geological age and geophysical signatures) (Ioane & Stanciu, 2015).

An important component of TTZ is the south-eastern continuation of the Polish Trough, a TESZ tectonic structure formed by extensional processes, having a particular crustal thickness and a thick pile of Mesozoic sediments. We consider that this geological structure, situated along the western boundary of the East European Platform, continues all along TESZ eastern boundary, in Romania being covered by the East Carpathians tectonic nappes. In Poland the Polish Trough was heavily investigated and nicely illustrated by refraction seismic experiments, while in Romania, only the Vrancea 2001 refraction seismic line (Fig. 3) crossed such a graben-like structure in the East Carpathians Bend Zone (Hauser et al., 2007).

After crossing the Vrancea seismogenic zone, the “Romanian Trough”, concealed beneath the Carpathians, turns its trend to south-west up to the Alexandria Depression.

Seismic tomography studies became during the last 25 years the main geophysical method to investigate lithospheric and mantelic structures using seismic velocity anomalies. When studying TESZ in the region where Romania is situated, the results published by Piromallo & Morelli (1997), Wortel & Spakman (2000), and more recently by Van de Meer et al. (2018a) are considered as highly significant. The East European Platform is interpreted in Fig. 4 as the blue elongated structure situated between 50 and 400 km depth, while the red slices located above it, at depths between 0 and 100 km, are interpreted as terranes accreted before the Permo-Triassic, suite of soft collision processes.

Fig. 3 – Cross section built on refraction seismic data at the East Carpathians Bend Zone. A deep Permo-Triassic graben and a 10-15 km crustal stretching have been interpreted here (Hauser et al., 2007)

Fig. 4 – Seismic tomography section across the Moesian Platform built using HADES Tomography Explorer v. Alpha 0.2.0 (van der Meer, 2018b)

A study dedicated to the Intramoesian Fault and relationships between the Moesian Platform (MP) compartments was based on recent seismicity data (2014-2017) with high accuracy positioning (Stanciu & Ioane, 2017). It was shown that the Intramoesian Fault is a quasi-vertical fault crossing the entire crust of the eastern compartment of Moesia. The contact between the two MP compartments is inclined and displaced some tens of km westward, suggesting soft collision processes during accretion of these two terranes (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 – Crustal seismicity section illustrating the inclined tectonic contact between the Moesian Platform compartments (Stanciu & Ioane, 2017)

Discussion and Conclusions

The main results of this study are summarized in Fig. 6 and discussed in the following:

The eastern boundary of TESZ, studied as TTZ in Poland, is continuing southward as was interpreted on satellite magnetic anomalies (Ioane & Stanciu, 2015). It crosses Ukraine and partly Romania beneath the East Carpathians sedimentary structures, and then the Moesian Platform in Romania and Bulgaria towards the Black Sea;

Data processing and interpretation of EGG 97 gravimetric geoid anomalies illustrated a good correlation between TESZ boundary and the NW-SE lineament of rapid variation of geoid heights. The sudden NE-SW trending shift of this lineament was interpreted as a westward displacement of the crustal and lithospheric structures due to wrench tectonics processes determined by the collision between Africa and Eurasia (Ioane & Stanciu, 2018);

Refraction seismics data on the Vrancea 2001 line crossing the East Carpathians Bend Zone were interpreted as a deep Permo-Triassic graben structure (Hauser et al., 20017), partly situated beneath the Carpathians sedimentary nappes. It resembles to a large extent the crustal structures in Poland, revealed by refraction seismic experiments across the TTZ;

The two high seismicity zones trending NE-SW, located at the East Carpathians Bend Zone, were recently interpreted as being associated with the deeply located Permo-Triassic graben boundaries, affected by extensional active tectonics (Ioane & Stanciu, 2018);

The Romanian Trough, considered at crustal depths at the western East European Platform (EEP) limit and concealed beneath East Carpathians and Moesian Platform younger sedimentary formations, was mainly interpreted on residual gravity anomalies (Ioane & Atanasiu, 2000).

The westward deepening of the East European Platform beneath the Moesian Platform, as interpreted on seismic tomography data using HADES software, is considered to illustrate traces of an old stage of terrane accretion, suite of post-subduction soft collisions.

Fig. 6 – TESZ boundary and the Romanian Trough in Romania and the Wrench tectonics model (Ioane & Stanciu, 2018). Black dashed lines: boundaries of the Romanian Trough, based on residual gravity anomalies; red dashed lines: western boundaries of the East European Platform; thin black lines: transcurrent faults; blue arrows: horizontal displacements due to wrench tectonics processes; black dots: seismic events during 2014-2017; grey line: western limit of high seismicity eastern MP compartment

The Precambrian age of both East European Platform and eastern compartment of Moesian Platform (Sandulescu & Visarion, 2000), as well as the presence within the latter of the banded iron formation (BIF), give the possibility to consider this compartment as a slice of Baltica. The high seismicity of the MP compartment, as compared to the lower seismicity regime in the western compartment, suggests important differences in petrographic and physical properties between them. The western high seismicity limit, situated at tens of km west of the Intramoesian Fault (Stanciu & Ioane, 2017), may represent the eastern TESZ boundary. Under such circumstances, the continuation of the Polish Trough with the Romanian Trough becomes possible at crustal depths.

The south-western continuation of TESZ boundary across the Moesian Platform, mainly evidenced by gravimetric geoid anomalies (Ioane & Stanciu, 2018) is most probably determined by the wrench tectonics system, with south-western displacements between the Carpathians and river Danube.

The south-western continuation of TESZ boundary across the Moesian Platform is also sustained by high heat flow and geothermic anomalies at 3,000m, as shown in the geothermal map of Romania (Veliciu et al., 1985), in good agreement with the high heat flow anomalies observed above TTZ in Poland (Majorowicz et al., 2003). The explanation of high heat flow given in Poland, considering thinner crust above the Polish Trough and uplifted upper mantle, may be valid for the sector between the Carpathians and Danube river in Romania, since thinner crust was also interpreted beneath the Permo-Triassic graben in the East Carpathians Bend Zone (Hauser et al., 2007).

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